

The Symbol of a Nation: Ginger Meggs and Australian National Identity

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The Australian Sunday comic strip 'Ginger Meggs' first appeared on 13 November 1921 in the Sydney *Sunday Sun*. Now in its seventieth year of publication it is one of the oldest continuing comic strips in the world. This longevity is itself noteworthy, but more significant is 'Ginger Meggs's' frequent deployment as a symbol of Australia. Two interrelated factors, the internal workings of the comic strip and the manifestations of the character Ginger outside the comic strip, created, and continue to create, a mythology centred on Ginger Meggs as the 'typical' Australian. Ginger Meggs's position in Australian culture is such that he is listed in *The Oxford Companion to Australian Literature* as 'Australia's most famous "boy" from the 1920s to the 1960s'.

One of the editors of the *Oxford Companion*, Barry Andrews, sufficiently intrigued by Ginger's position in Australian culture, wrote a piece on the strip for a collection of essays on Australian cultural history, *Nellie Melba, Ginger Meggs and Friends*. Andrews's essay attempted to establish the reasons for Ginger's success and relate that success to the history of twentieth-century Australia. He stated that 'the strip was recognisably Australian without being too localised' because its creator, James Bancks (1889-1952), chose to set it in an urban/rural crossroads, similar to Hornsby on Sydney's northern outskirts, where Bancks spent his childhood. The Meggs's, according to Andrew's, 'hovered somewhere near the middle range' economically. John Meggs worked in a white collar job, was a mason, and entertained his boss at home. Nonetheless Sarah Meggs sold eggs to make ends meet.¹ Andrews argued that the first fifty strips published between 1921 and 1922 established three basic types of stories that featured Ginger, as battler, confidence man, and mischief maker. He found these themes recurred in three other samples of fifty strips selected from those published between 1933-36, 1946-52, and 1978-79. In these stories, in the urban/rural setting, and through Bancks's use of an ironic 'you can't win' humour, Andrews believed Australians recognised themselves.

Andrews acknowledged the limitations of identifying Ginger Meggs as representative of a national type, given that such concepts

¹ Barry Andrews, 'Ginger Meggs: His Story' in Susan Dermody, John Docker and Drusilla Modjeska (eds), *Nellie Melba, Ginger Meggs and Friends*, Malmesbury, 1992, p. 213. The strip was drawn by Bancks until 1952, when he died, and then by Ron Vivan (1953-1974), Lloyd Piper (1974-1984) and since 18 March 1984 by James Kemsley.

overlook and marginalise ethnic and gender diversity, but he said Ginger 'can be seen within the tradition of how at least some Australians used to see the nation itself: as the young, vigorous, independent, cheeky new country, irreverently cocking a snook at Europe and the old world'.² He concluded his essay with the worry that by 1981 Ginger Meggs had lost touch with the folk who constitute Australia and saw 'his' only hope as a closer alignment with the forces that 'determine mass taste'.³ To establish how out of touch the strip was in 1981 would require a separate study but when James Kemsley took it over in 1984 'Ginger Meggs' re-blossomed and by 1986-87 Ginger was evoked as a symbol of Australia, and more simply as a typical Australian boy, across broad dimensions of the culture.

In general I agree with Andrews's outline of Ginger Meggs's relationship with a gender and ethnic specific Australian national type.⁴ But Andrews underplayed the contribution of 'Ginger Meggs' to the construction of that national type. He paid too little attention to the way 'Ginger Meggs' mediates for an Australian audience aspects of Australian culture that are borrowed from America. In Andrews's presentation Ginger Meggs reflected Australian character. He assigned the comic strip a passive role in relation to a static culture. But 'Ginger Meggs' is an active agent and that culture is a dynamic force. To understand the construction of the myth around Ginger Meggs a brief overview of the development of the comic strip in Australia is needed.

Historical Development of the Comic Art Form in Australia

A number of illustrated journals existed in Australia in the nineteenth century, but it was not until the establishment of the *Bulletin* in 1880 that the comic art form found a medium in which it could develop. Unlike earlier journals, the *Bulletin* was inspired by American newspapers and magazines such as the *San Francisco Chronicle* and *Scribners*, rather than English journals such as *Punch*. William Traill, an early editor of the *Bulletin*, admired the quality of illustration in American magazines.⁵ Moreover, the *Bulletin*, with its banner slogan 'Australia for Australians', and later 'Australia for the White Man', was an important contributor to a nascent Australian nationalism.

The *Bulletin's* nationalism needs to be examined because this has become central to the debate about Australian national identity. Sylvia Lawson in her book *The Archibald Paradox*, a work about J.F. Archibald a founder of the *Bulletin*, explained that

2. Andrews, op. cit., p. 225.

3. *ibid.*, p. 229.

4. As I no longer live in Australia it is hard to stay current with Ginger's development, but the 1 July 1990 episode, in which Ginger fell asleep at school because he had been watching the World Cup soccer, suggests a broader 'Australian' identity.

5. Sylvia Lawson, *The Archibald Paradox*, Sydney, 1983, pp. 66-67.

The Archibald paradox is simply the paradox of being colonial. Metropolis, the centre of language, of the dominant culture and its judgements, lies away in the great Elsewhere; but the tasks of living, communicating, teaching, acting-out and changing the culture must be carried on not Elsewhere but Here. To know enough of the metropolitan world, colonials must, in limited ways at least, move and think internationally; to resist it strongly enough for the colony to cease to be colonial and become its own place, they must become nationalists.⁶

Following Lawson's concept of paradox I would tentatively suggest that the *Bulletin* drew inspiration from America as a means of resisting Britain. If Britain was still the metropolis, America at least proved that indigenous nationalism was a viable alternative to colonial status. Although, ironically enough, America was swiftly becoming the new metropolitan centre, particularly in regard to technical innovation.

The quality of illustrations in American journals relied on new photo-mechanical processes of plate making. To obtain this quality of reproduction the *Bulletin* in 1883 imported as its first staff artist the American Livingston Hopkins, who signed his work Hop, and a team of American photogravure plate-makers. At the crude technological level the comic strip, as distinct from the cartoon, owes its existence to photomechanical reproduction. Before photogravure the combination of graphic and text was a tedious and expensive process. Equally important to the development of comic strips were mass circulated newspapers that employed them as a weapon in their drive for greater circulation. The *Bulletin* was not a newspaper but it introduced the technology, and provided a forum for artists, that formed a base for the development of comic strips in Australia. In the 1920s, when a suburban boom provided a market for mass circulated newspapers, artists were able to supply them with comic strips.

Locating Ginger Meggs

Just as the *Bulletin* was a local experience of a Western cultural form so too was 'Ginger Meggs'. 'Ginger Meggs's' creator James Bancks left school when he was fourteen and worked as an office boy, wool clerk, and lift driver. He practiced drawing in his spare time. His first published cartoons appeared in the *Comic Australian*, a short lived journal, in 1911. In August 1914 his work appeared in the *Bulletin* and he joined its staff shortly thereafter at the salary of eight pounds a week. At the same time he began to take lessons from Julian Ashton, a member of the Heidelberg School. Bancks also free-lanced for the *Sunday Sun*. In 1921 he submitted a comic strip about a young girl, Gladys Gladys, under the title 'Us Fellers', to the new Sunday comic strip/children's supplement *Sunbeams*. By February 1922 Gladys had disappeared and the strip focused on a googly bowler from the first strip – Ginger Meggs. Ginger's

6. *ibid.*, p. ix.

lineage included both the *Bulletin's* 'Little Boy From Manly' as well as the American strips 'The Yellow Kid', 'The Katzenjammer Kids', 'Buster Brown', 'The Toonerville Trolley', and 'Reg'lar Fellers'.

The *Bulletin's* 'Little Boy From Manly' was first used in April 1885 to represent young Australia's folly in contributing to Britain's imperial campaign in the Sudan. The Boy became a symbolic device for Australia in the *Bulletin* until after the Great War when the image of the ANZAC digger emerged. In taking up the symbolic legacy of 'The Little Boy From Manly' Ginger in part maintained the vision of an earlier more innocent Australia. But it was a vision tempered by the War and its outcome. The first episode of another early Australian comic strip, 'You and Me', published in *Smith's Weekly* 4 September 1920, in which the two protagonists argue over conscription, party politics, and Melbourne versus Sydney rivalry, in that order, suggests that the War extenuated fissures in Australian society. Indeed *Smith's Weekly*, which had an all Australian material policy and encouraged nostalgia for the 'good old days' when the soldiers were all mates together, was a manifestation of the desire to establish some sort of social order to replace that shattered by the Great War. It is more than ironic that *Smith's Weekly* turned to the American born Stan Cross and asked him to develop a strip similar to the American domestic humour strip 'The Gumps'. This occurrence was part of an heightened incursion of American 'popular' forms in Australian culture. Although the early episodes of Cross's 'You and Me' were highly political the strip soon settled into the domestic humour vein familiar to those of us who still read it today under its current title 'The Potts'.⁷

Smith's Weekly was not the first Australian publication to borrow from American sources to develop local comic strips. American comic strips were well enough known in Australia that Hugh McCrae copied 'The Katzenjammer Kids' in his 1911 comic strip 'Jim and Jam', which ran in the *Comic Australian*. The first 'Ginger Meggs' strip not only used an art style, and setting, similar to 'The Toonerville Trolley' and 'Reg'lar Fellers', but borrowed the theme of its gag from the former and its original title from the latter. 'Ginger Meggs' also borrowed gags from 'Skippy' another American comic strip.⁸ When 'Ginger Meggs' is

7 For more details on Stan Cross see John Ryan, *Panel by Panel*, Sydney, 1979, p. 18 and *passim*. For a discussion of *Smith's Weekly* see Vane Lindesay, *The Inked in Image*, Melbourne, 1979, pp. 25-33; and my 'Stop Laughing This Is Serious: The Comic Art Form and Australian Identity, 1880-1960', BA Honours Thesis, Department of History, University of Sydney, 1986, pp. 36-39. See the latter Chapter 2 and Richard White, 'Combating Cultural Aggression: Australian Opposition to Americanization', *Meanjin*, vol. 39, 1980, pp. 275-289 for a discussion of 'Americanization'.

8. Both 'The Toonerville Trolley' and 'Ginger Meggs' were set in communities on the outskirts of large urban centres. The first 'Ginger Meggs' episode adapted a gag, about breaking a window with a baseball, that had appeared in a pre 1921 'Toonerville Trolley'. In the 'Ginger Meggs' version the gag revolved around Gladstone Gladys's sweet talking the outraged owner of the window.

'Skippy' was created by Percy Crosby in the early 1920s. Both Skippy and Ginger at different times flipped coins to decide whether to indulge themselves or do the right thing. When the coin toss did not suit either of them they re-threw until they got a favourable outcome. James Kemsley the current *auteur* of 'Ginger Meggs' drew attention to this occurrence but it is difficult to assign the origins of the joke. Bancks used the gag, at least twice in the *Sun*, on 1 November 1925 and on 26 April 1942. Crosby's use of the gag may not have occurred until after 1928 as the reprint of it in a collection (Jerry Robinson, (ed.) *Skippy and Percy Crosby*, New York, 1978, p. 150.) has a King Features copyright logo and Crosby did not work with that corporation until after 1928. In any case, 'Skippy' was used as model for another Australian comic strip of the 1920s - Syd Nichols's 'Fatty Fin'. This information comes from Jim Russell the *auteur* of 'The Potts' and a contemporary of Bancks and Nichols. Author's conversation with James Kemsley and Jim Russell, 20 May 1987. It is also worth noting that the female character of 'The Gumps' and Ginger's girlfriend were both named Min.

presented as a symbol of Australia the debt it owes to America for, its means of production, its style, and on occasions its content, is overlooked. This suppression of history is an important factor in the operation of Ginger's mythology. It is but one of the ways the comic strip seeks to put reality at a distance.

Understanding the relationship between a comic strip and the society in which it appears in is crucial to any reading of a strip. The comic strip is a field of experience constructed for the purpose of entertainment. To create humour, or a sense of adventure, reality is put at a distance. But there must be some recognisable features within the strip or it would be incomprehensible. The degree of recognisable elements varies from strip to strip but generally there is a suspension of temporality and place in comics, especially long running comics. The suspension of reality in comic strips is signalled by their structural features. These consist of:

- 1) a narrative told by a sequence of pictures (panels).
- 2) a continuing cast of characters or character.
- 3) text or dialogue within the pictures (usually word balloons).⁹

'Ginger Meggs' is played out in a time and space that echoes the past and the present; that echoes both Western universal forms and an Australian identity. 'Ginger Meggs' longevity allows it to posit its own internal reality.

For instance, even the Second World War did not disrupt Ginger's world. From 1940-1944 the 'Ginger Meggs' comic strip continued as normal. Ginger's father was not conscripted, the Meggs family suffered no greater shortages than normal, coupons did not appear in the strip, and there was hardly a direct mention of the War. It is useful to remember that by this stage the strip's audience was close to three million readers in a population of less than eight million.¹⁰ A large percentage of its readers were adults. The presence of posters urging the purchase of war bonds and red cross seals that occasionally appeared in the strip's background were no doubt indirect appeals to those adult readers. On two occasions, 20 October 1940 and 14 December 1942, there were direct appeals for the war effort. Similarly on 17 October 1943 General MacArthur appeared in the strip. Humorously on 22 November 1942 Ginger and the Fellers managed to shoot down a Japanese war plane using a giant skyrocket. But that was the limit, four strips out of two hundred. Indeed so distant was 'Ginger Meggs' from the War that in 1941, when Australia had been in the War for almost two years, the Italian greengrocer 'Dago Joe' twice appeared (6 July and 17 August) in his normal role of the stereotyped Italian in the Australian community. And, although Bancks drew a recruitment poster for air raid wardens he did not include characters from the strip. Such evidence demonstrates how 'Ginger Meggs' held major events at a distance yet remained topical. Symbols of the War, General MacArthur and a Japanese pilot,

⁹ Robert Harvey, 'The Aesthetics of the Comic Strip', *Journal of Popular Culture*, vol. 12, 1979, p. 64.

¹⁰ F.E. Baume, 'How Meggs Made His Creator Rich and Famous', *Sunday Sun*, 26 May 1935.

FAMILY TIES

were introduced, but the War itself had no effect on the overall structure of the strip. 'Ginger Meggs' preserved a reassuring static image of Australia at a time of national anxiety. It may be that just as American soldiers fought the War to maintain the right to drink Coca-Cola, as one soldier put it in a letter home, Australians fought the War to maintain a society they saw typified by 'Ginger Meggs'.¹¹ In any case the comic strip maintained its own image of a past reality and suggested the promise of an ideal future. The ability of the comic strip to put reality at a distance relied not so much on the absence of current content but on the overall structure of the comic strip. Indeed the structure of a comic strip allows it to utilise a good deal of present content without destroying the strip's internal coherence.

A close reading of two episodes of 'Ginger Meggs' reveals how a structure, consisting of codes and conventions, operates to suppress external reality in the comic strip and at the same time allows the strip to assume mythological dimensions. One episode 'Family Ties' was published 1 June, 1952 in the *Sunday Telegraph* and reproduced in two editions of *The Golden Years of Ginger Meggs* a collection of 'Ginger Meggs' strips.¹² The second episode is untitled, but 'Fourth of July' is an appropriate title, appeared on 30 June 1985 in the *Sun Herald*. This thirty four year difference allows us to see the long term operation of a number of codes and conventions. Both of these episodes involve a dialogue between Ginger and his mother Sarah. The only other characters present are Tony, Ginger's pet monkey, Mike, his dog, and the family cat. Tony and Mike are Ginger's constant companions. They are mime characters used to give an interpretation to Ginger's words and actions. The family cat is used as a sign that Ginger is in his own house and serves as a supplementary interpreter of Ginger. When Ginger is out of the house this latter role is performed by a selection of stock characters. In the sixth panel of 'Fourth of July' when Ginger's oratory has won the day, Tony is happy, the family cat is pleasantly impressed and Mike's expression is nonchalant, as if it was never in doubt that Ginger would win. A more obvious convention is the clothing of the characters. Ginger is always dressed in red shorts and shoes, white shirt and black waist coat. Sarah always wears a yellow frock with red and black polka dots.

In addition to these conventions there is an encoding created by the format of the comic as a combination of both text and graphic. The grammar of graphics that this combination creates affects the way in which the comic is read. There is a relationship between the ability to use this combination fully and the existence of the comic, and the readers' knowledge of it as a continuous reality. The long running comic strip through its aforementioned conventions sets up a sort of structure (langue) from which a practice of present content (parole) is played out. 'Family Ties' and 'Fourth of July', both of which set up the same punch

11 E.J. Kahn Jr., *The Big Drink: The Story of Coca-Cola*, New York, 1960, p. 13.
12 John Horgan, (ed.), *The Golden Years of Ginger Meggs*, Sydney, 1978, p. 189.

line, reveal this operation. In the former Ginger is trying to extradite himself from some wrong. In the latter he is trying to persuade his mother to condone a less than legal action. In 'Family Ties' Sarah responds verbally to Ginger's oratory throughout the strip. In the final panel she delivers the punch line – 'He blinded me with science! I wonder if I'm rearing a great lawyer or a gangster? I must do something when I'm not so dizzy'. These comments are addressed to Tony, Mike and the family cat from a lounge chair – Sarah has had to sit down because she is dizzy. In 'Fourth of July' Sarah has responded to Ginger's oratory only with looks and glances until the second last panel where she equivocates – 'Er well ... um ... I ... suppose ... since ... you ... but'. The punch line she delivers in the final panel is – 'He's bound to end up a great lawyer; either that or needing one'. This is addressed solely to the family cat, Tony and Mike having correctly left with Ginger. Sarah holds the cat possibly to support or distract herself from what she has just done – condoned Ginger wagging school.

'Fourth of July' uses so little text to set up the joke because the character and abilities of Ginger are well known to the audience and because the audience's ability to perceive meaning through visual presentation has been heightened by movies, photo-journalism, advertising, and television. Except for the last panels the text is almost unnecessary – a minor part of setting up the punch line. Because of this the text is able to assume another role, uttering a message other than the joke. I will return to this point later.

A further reason that 'Fourth of July' is able to use a sparse text is the relation of the comic strip to its historical location. This location is revealed by a comparison of the two punch lines. In 1951 Sarah 'wonders' if she is 'rearing a great lawyer or a gangster'. In 1985 she no longer wonders. Ginger now is 'bound to end up a great lawyer ... or needing one'. There is a shift from wonder to certainty. There is also a subtle shift in binary oppositions. The opposite of a great lawyer is no longer a gangster, that is a criminal, but somebody who needs a great lawyer. The shift in oppositions was almost mandatory, because the notion of criminality was no longer as certain as in the 1950s. In the mid to late 1980s a crusading press accused politicians and judges of corruption and the *Sydney Morning Herald's* 'Stay in Touch' column joked that crime was a spectator sport in New South Wales. If politicians and judges were corrupt in the 1950s they were not the subject of daily accusations in the media.

The punch line of 'Fourth of July' is an example of the comic strip as mythologiser. Myth here is understood as Roland Barthes sees it – 'that is a system of communication, a message, a signification, a form defined not by the object of its message but the way in which it utters this message'.¹³ By making a joke about Ginger needing a lawyer because

13 Roland Barthes, 'Myth Today', in *Mythologies*, London 1972, p. 109.

of his glib tongue the strip suggests to its readers that if Ginger, the embodiment of national identity, may need a lawyer on occasion then it is only natural that other prominent Australians should require legal services from time to time. Ginger accommodates himself to changing times, preserves the internal reality of the strip, and naturalises the concept of 'corrupt' politicians and lawyers.

By itself the final panel of 'Fourth of July' would not convey its message as strongly. It is reinforced by the text in the other panels of the strip. While these convey a message about the influence of America on Australia they also preserve and represent the synchronic set of codes that form the essence of 'Ginger Meggs'. The message can be delivered in direct language but it has to be worked into the field of experience of 'Ginger Meggs'. This is achieved in the first panel by showing a long wide shot of the Meggs's house. It is not a modern home, belonging instead to the 1920s. Its setting in the current epoch is only partial. While it has a television aerial and there are modern delivery vans parked in the street, the house itself has an old style ornate picket fence. Also the figures depicted in the street are dressed in 'Ginger Meggs' style – a cartoon 1920s style. From the house Ginger and his mother can be heard arguing over whether Ginger should go to school on the Fourth of July. In the next three panels Ginger lists the facets of American society shared by Australia – tv, movies, cars, planes, dollars and cents, Kentucky Fried Chicken and McDonalds. With hand on heart Ginger then tells his mother (and us) that 'America is more than just another country, it's part of our heritage! We should celebrate that'. Sarah Meggs can not withstand this logic and Ginger triumphs.

'Ginger Meggs' here is an example of Roland Barthes conception of myth. The signification or form is the strip itself and the character Ginger. It has emptied itself of its meaning – its history, the knowledge of the past that it postulates – all this has been put at a distance. As Barthes notes myth 'transfers history into nature'. In the eyes of the myth consumer the intention 'of the concept can remain manifest without however appearing to have an interest in the matter'.¹⁴ If Ginger's oratory can be read ironically then the irony is subsumed by its location in a comic strip: the irony becomes simply a comic strip joke, such is the form of comic strips. True the strip contains a tension about the Australian-American relationship but it is the containment of this tension, and turning it to good use (a day off school), that is the point of the strip. In other words 'Ginger Meggs' makes us accept as natural an American influence on Australia. The ability to accept both present content and past structure in the strip ironically corresponds with the acceptance of Ginger Meggs as a distinctive Australian character within a structure borrowed from America.

To explain the process of myth making at work in 'Ginger Meggs' it is necessary to add a further step to Barthes's concept of myth to avoid

¹⁴ Barthes, *op. cit.*, p. 129.

his somewhat static treatment of myth and culture. Two histories are suppressed in the comic strip. First, the strip's relation to the history of Australian society and second, the history of the comic strip itself. These two histories are closely interwoven but they can be separated for analytical purposes.

In the seventy year history of 'Ginger Meggs' there has been only two occasions when the history of the strip has been mentioned in the strip itself. The first when the strip moved from the *Sun Herald* to the *Sunday Telegraph* in 1951 and the second when it moved back to the *Sun Herald* in 1978. In an episode published 3 June 1951 John Meggs announced to Sarah, 'We are going into a new newspaper'. Sarah replied that she was not going anywhere unless she got a new dress. In the next panel the family met with Mr. Bancks and Sarah complained that she had been in the same dress for twenty-nine years. Bancks replied that she looks beautiful in it so he can not alter it. The rest of the episode affirmed that nothing would change in the move to the *Sunday Telegraph*. The episode served a number of functions. First, it was an advertisement for Ginger's move to the *Sunday Telegraph*. Second, it was an affirmation of the strip's continued legitimacy; nothing was to change. To reaffirm that message the artist himself appeared in the strip. Incidentally, Bancks depicted himself as though he occupied a previously unseen room in the Meggs's house suggesting perhaps that he was an anthropologist and the strip simply thick description. At a time of crisis for the strip, there was a law suit regarding the change of newspapers, Bancks reached for the essential elements that ensured the strip's popularity: its thirty years of existence, its basic formula, and his own position as artist, to sell its readers on the shift to the *Sunday Telegraph*. Readers who week after week suppressed their knowledge that Ginger had been around for years, so that they might enjoy his weekly adventure, were reminded that the strip had a history that set it apart from other strips and contributed to the readers' pleasure. That is readers derived pleasure from the strip by repressing their knowledge of its basic framework in order to let an individual story unfold. That repressed knowledge could be called on not only to sell the strip but to sell other products and messages.

For example, *The Draper of Australasia* reported in its 31 March 1930 issue that Grace Brothers, a large Sydney department store, 'staged an elaborate series of tableaux' over the Christmas season featuring the 'Ginger Meggs' story 'Bennie's Brainwave'. In the same period 'Ginger Meggs' song books were published by Allans, a Melbourne based music publisher. According to Robert Holden a good deal of 'Ginger Meggs' memorabilia was produced in the late 1920s.¹⁵ I suspect that this activity reflected a similar trend in America where comic strip characters, such as Buster Brown, were used as trade logos for a number of products and the comic-art form was adopted by the advertising industry as an effective medium to market products. 'Ginger Meggs' seems to have been the sole

15 Robert Holden, *A Birthday Celebration for Ginger Meggs*, [exhibitiopn catalogue], Sydney 1986.

Australian comic strip accorded this treatment and only in a limited and partial fashion, probably due to the smaller scale of the Australian economy and its different state of development. With the resurgence of the strip, under James Kemsley, 'Ginger Meggs' has been used for a number of other commercial purposes and Ginger's longevity and status as national symbol are stressed. Here the strip's relationship to Australian society is important. Nonetheless Ginger is more than a marketing tool. His usefulness to advertisers lies in his universal (Australian) acceptance.

Although I argue that Ginger Meggs's personification of Australian identity is a myth it is important to acknowledge that he is regarded by many as a symbol of Australia. That after all is the nature of myth. The comic strip itself can never address this status directly but its popularity and the merchandising uses to which it is put rely on this status. For instance the plate issued to celebrate Ginger's sixty-fifth birthday emphasised the strip's longevity and its place in Australian history. Ginger's appearances outside the comic strip add to his symbolic status. The more media in which the character appears the stronger the myth because myth relies on repetition and adaptability to different circumstances. Ginger is not all things to all Australians but he is enough to a significant proportion to serve as a symbol. For example, the historian Richard White regards the 1920s Ginger as representative of Australian character in that era. A Ginger Meggs sweater was marketed in the 1940s.¹⁶ In the 1950s Ginger sold dental hygiene for the NSW Department of Health. The playwright and producer Ken Horler used the decline of 'Ginger Meggs' in the 1970s as a metaphor for Australia's endangered cultural distinctiveness. In 1985 the Post Office issued a Ginger Meggs stamp as part of a series on Australian children's literary characters. Shortly after *Australian Society* pictured Ginger on its front cover as representative of Australian characteristics. And the *Sydney Morning Herald* equated a paper boy's decision to continue in his job after being robbed with the pluck of Ginger.¹⁷

In early 1987 Ginger appeared around Sydney in four concurrent representations. Grace Brothers used him as a marketing tool for a sale, and even ran a Ginger Meggs look a like contest at a suburban Mall. At Bondi Beach, itself an Australian symbol, a graffiti punk Ginger appeared on the beach wall. In Oxford Street, Paddington Ginger and company were on display as objects d'art. And in the *Sydney Morning Herald* an editorial cartoon used Ginger to represent the fate that might lie in wait for the Australian economy. All four of the images reinforced each other. Surely Ginger is an appropriate symbol of Australia if he appears at Bondi Beach, Paddington and in Grace Brothers stores? And what better spokesperson for a department store than a symbol of the nation? For the rebellious graffiti artist what better figure to reclaim for the larrikin

16 Advertising the item in the 6 November 1949 episode of 'Ginger Meggs' Bancks used the American term 'sweater' not the Australian 'jumper'.

17 Richard White, *Inventing Australia*, Sydney, 1981, p. 123; 'Ginger Meggs', *Sydney Sun*, 6 November 1949; Andrews, p. 227; *Australian Society*, April 1986; *Sydney Morning Herald*, 12 May 1986.

tradition than a symbol of the nation and one that a would-be avant-garde pays 'big bucks' for in Paddington?¹⁸

These incidents show that 'Ginger Meggs' is more than a comic strip character who is occasionally licensed to merchandisers by his creator. Ginger is claimed by a broad sector of the population. The comic strip evokes both a Ginger who shops at Grace Brothers and a Ginger who shop lifts. The myth surrounding Ginger and the structure of the comic strip naturalise his symbolic status but when history is called upon to explain present content in the strip, and when the operation of the myth is detailed, it becomes clear that within the limits of its gender and ethnic specificity Ginger Meggs is a contested symbol of Australia.

18 *Sydney Morning Herald*, 11 May 1987.